

MEASURES TO PREVENT OCCUPATIONAL DISEASES AT WORK

¹Shovkiddin Narziev Murtozaevich, ²Mudarisova Rayxon Khojievna

¹Professor, PhD, Associate Professor of Tashkent State Technical University

²Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor Uzbek State University of World
Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10214297>

Abstract. *The article examines the role of pedagogical technologies in training specialists in the field of labor protection and ways to improve the efficiency of their use, as well as specific methods of innovative pedagogical technologies that are convenient and easy to learn by students. Recommendations are given on the mechanism for revising effective teaching methods.*

Keywords: *labor protection, occupational diseases, periodic medical examination, harmful factor, therapeutic and prophylactic risk factor, working personnel, biological factor, chemical factor.*

Introduction

Since labor protection includes a set of laws, socio-economic, organizational, technical, hygienic, preventive measures aimed at ensuring the efficiency, health and safety of a person in the process of work, the working conditions of citizens in all areas should be created at the proper level [1,2].

Measures to reduce occupational diseases in industrial enterprises, manufacture or purchase of devices and devices to protect workers from various harmful effects of substances, installation of air exchangers and air conditioning systems, retrofitting of old types, fencing space for the release of substances instead of conventional methods of air exchange, aspiration method, the use of advanced machines, monitoring systems, air composition, etc. d. installation of tools, etc. are examples [3,4,5].

Protecting and strengthening the health of working personnel is an important task of national importance [1,6].

Well-being is not only the absence of diseases, but also a high level of physical and mental endurance. An important place in healthcare is occupied by the state of labor activity. therefore, the improvement of working conditions and the prevention of occupational diseases has an important impact on the economic development of our republic: The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the law "on sanitary supervision in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "basic provisions on public health protection in the Republic of Uzbekistan", important legal documents aimed at ensuring safety and improving working conditions in all industries, transport and agriculture. and others confirm our point of view [4,8].

Research methods and results

Occupational disease is determined taking into account harmful factors of production. This is a physical form of the disease (occupational deafness, vibration sickness, radiation sickness, caisson disease, altitude sickness, etc.), biological (infectious and parasitic diseases: brucellosis, anthrax) and chemical factors (poisoning), with prolonged inhalation of certain powders (pneumoconiosis, bronchitis, etc.), and also distinguish the types that occur during physical

exertion or injury (neuritis, bursitis). Its origin is also associated with excessive depletion of the body and a decrease in its ability to fight the disease (see figure) [1,5].

According to a recent study by the World Health Organization on the assessment of the most common occupational risk factors, at least 1.6% of the disease burden in European countries is caused by working conditions.

According to the study, the main risk factors are: injuries (40 percent), noise (22 percent), carcinogens (18 percent), hazardous particles and ergonomic factors (3 percent).

However, back pain (37 percent), hearing loss (16 percent), lung injury-related diseases (13 percent), asthma (11 percent) and cancer (9 percent) were cited as the occupational burden of chronic diseases.

Occupational diseases are approved on the basis of the list of occupational diseases based on the etiological principle in force in Uzbekistan, namely Appendix No. 2 to Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 195 of July 1, 2011.

Fig. Factors of occurrence of occupational diseases

In our Republic, medical and sanitary services for employees of industrial and agricultural enterprises are carried out in two directions:

1. Protection and improvement of working conditions.
2. Provision of medical and preventive care.

Protecting and improving the health of industrial and agricultural workers is one of the tasks of the centers of sanitary and epidemiological surveillance.

Dispensary supervision of employees exposed to occupational harmful factors is important for the prevention of occupational diseases [1,5,6].

Medical examinations (primary and periodic) are one of the forms of dispensary observation and are of great importance in providing medical care to

Medical examinations of working personnel are therapeutic and preventive measures carried out in order to identify changes in the state of health of personnel and medical contraindications to work, as well as to protect public health, prevent the occurrence and spread of diseases [2,3].

Considerations

Medical examinations of workers and employees are divided into the following types:

Preliminary-medical examinations conducted in order to establish medical regulations in relation to the profession.

Periodic - medical examinations carried out in the course of work.

The purpose of periodic medical examinations:

-a determination of the conformity of the health of workers and service personnel to the work they perform;

- dynamic monitoring of the health status of working personnel under the conditions of exposure to occupational damage;
- prevention of occupational diseases and timely detection of their initial signs;
- the identification of common diseases that prevent the continuation of work with harmful and dangerous factors of production;
- accident prevention on the appointment and conduct of therapeutic and preventive measures.

Periodic medical examination provides an indication of the periodicity established by law, the conditions under which the employee and service personnel perform their work or activities. The frequency of medical examination will depend on the time required to monitor changes in the health status of the employee, the purpose of the medical examination, and in some cases, the age of the medical examination.

For example, underage employees are required to undergo annual medical examinations until they reach the age of 18. Young workers engaged in harmful work must undergo annual medical examinations until they reach the age of 21.

At the same time, on certain types of work, an operational determination of the employee's health status is required, a health check before proceeding directly to each work activity. To do this, a preflight or duty medical examination is carried out. They can be included in the type of permanent medical examination [3].

Along with the above-mentioned medical examinations, extraordinary (unscheduled) medical examinations may be carried out. Medical examination is carried out mainly by employers or at the request of working employees, as well as in accordance with medical recommendations in order to detect the presence of occupational diseases.

Medical examinations of working personnel can be divided into two groups:

Group I-medical examinations conducted for the purpose of checking the professional suitability of employees and the prevention of occupational diseases.

Such examinations should take place:

- persons engaged in heavy work and under the influence of harmful and unfavorable factors of working conditions (including those working in underground conditions);
- a workers engaged in work related to the movement of vehicles;
- persons under the age of 18, etc.

Group II-medical examinations conducted in order to protect public health, ensure sanitary and epidemiological safety (prevention of the development and spread of infectious diseases).

Such examinations should take place:

- enterprises of the food industry and public catering;
- a sanitary installations and sanitary equipment in the field of drinking water supply;
- a staff of medical-preventive and children's institutions;
- other institutions, etc.

The preventive orientation of occupational pathology is carried out primarily through periodic medical examinations of persons working in harmful and unfavorable working conditions.

Primary periodic medical examinations are aimed at preventing the employment of persons who have certain changes in the organs and systems of the body and are not allowed to work under the influence of harmful professional factors [1]. Such surveys are primarily aimed at the prevention of occupational diseases and rational employment, taking into account the state of

health of the employee entering the workplace. that is, aimed at determining the medical regulations for admission to classes related to exposure to harmful factors is one of the conditions that create preventive measures, therefore, it is necessary to take into account:

- compliance with personal protection measures;
- full implementation of measures covering biophysiological methods of prevention;
- high-quality preliminary medical examination before hiring;
- control over the quality of the preliminary medical examination before hiring;
- a new look at a healthy lifestyle, the requirement of healthy working conditions for employees. teach to pay attention to your own health;
- activation of sanitary and rescue operations;
- for the purposes of primary prevention, to train medical workers in measures for the development of a healthy lifestyle.

In order to implement the above measures, it is necessary to create a mechanism that ensures and controls their implementation, as well as mandatory participation of the administration of enterprises in carrying out measures aimed at preventing occupational diseases, and filling out legal acts indicating bilateral (employer and employee) responsibilities [6,7].

To carry out differentiated dispensary control when drawing up the final report after a periodic medical examination, it is advisable to distinguish the following groups:

Dispensary groups:

D1-persons without the influence of harmful factors and unfavorable working conditions.

D2-persons who may develop occupational diseases.

D3-patients with occupational diseases.

Dispensary control groups are organized taking into account the nature of individual pathological signs or factors affecting their joint course, and the nature of the pathology they cause. Of great importance in preserving the health of the working population is the timely identification of a risk group for the development of occupational diseases within the framework of preventive measures and the implementation of a medical and wellness complex for them. Patients with occupational diseases are included in group D3, and their dispensary control is carried out on the basis of a special order of the Ministry of Health.

However, it is necessary to take into account and remember the following:

All patients should be taken under medical supervision as soon as an occupational disease is detected, including in cases where the initial clinic of the disease is poorly expressed.

Patients with occupational diseases are required to be constantly on treatment and dispensary control, regardless of whether they work or are retired.

The principles of dispensary observation of patients are determined by the form and features of the course of occupational diseases.

In order to prevent outbreaks and complications of occupational diseases, it is necessary that all patients with pronounced forms of occupational diseases are treated annually at the occupational diseases clinic.

Of particular importance is the proper employment of patients with occupational diseases in the dispensary monitoring system, which is an integral part of the rehabilitation of patients.

Conclusion

To prevent diseases caused by heat, reduce workplace overheating, a number of methodological and sanitary-hygienic measures are carried out. For this purpose, thermal

insulation materials, refrigeration and air exchange devices, special personal protective equipment are used.

In order to prevent colds, handlers need to be provided with special clothing, warm shoes, nutritious hot food, while special rooms for heating and rest should be allocated to them. People working in low temperature conditions must be examined.

When solving issues of medical and labor expertise, it should be based on how pronounced the process launched due to the laser beam is and how effective the therapeutic measures are.

REFERENCES

1. Makhmudova Sh.K. Textbook for professional medical universities. - T.: "Generation of the new century", 2011. 408 P.
2. Suleymanovich S. S. et al. Methods of forecasting and occurrence of traumatic damages i sport //International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering. – 2019. – T. 8. – №. 9 S2. – C. 223-225.
3. Suleymanovich S. S., Murtozayevich N. S. Studying and accounting sports injuries //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 7. – C. 759-763.
4. Shovkiddin N. et al. PROVISION OF LABOR PROTECTION AND ANALYSIS OF INJURIES OF ACTIVE PARTICIPANTS //Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol. – 2021. – T. 27. – №. 2
5. Narziev SHOVKIDDIN MURTOZAEVICH, Rakhimova Aziza Hassan Kizi APPLICATION and ANALYSIS of PEDAGOGICAL methods in the EDUCATIONAL PROCESS // TECHuka. 2021. No. 1 (5). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/primenenie-i-analiz-pedagogicheskikh-metodov-v-uchebnom-protseesse> (data of the appeal: 08.04.2021).
6. Narziev Shavkiddin Murtozaevich, Botirov Akbar Bahriddinovich HUMAN ACTIVITY SAFETY METHODS OF STUDYING AND ANALYZING RISKS IN THE LABOR PROCESS // Tesnik. 2021. No. 1 (5). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bezopasnost-deyatelnosti-cheloveka-metody-izucheniya-i-analiza-riskov-v-trudovom-protseesse> (accessed: 08.04.2021).
7. Narziev S., Latibov S. Methods Of Ensuring Occupational Safety And Health In Sports //The American Journal of Engineering and Technology. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 04. – C. 89-94.\
8. Narziev S., Asqarov J., Khokimyatov A. Methodology Of Organization Of The Labor Process And Preservation Of Employees' Health //The American Journal of Engineering and Technology. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 04. – C. 79-84.